

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

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INVESTIGATION OF THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF ELECTRICAL DISCHARGES IN LIQUIDS

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Abstract

The paper deals with the occurrence of high pressure as a result of high-voltage electric discharge between electrodes immersed in liquid. The electrical parameters of high-voltage electric pulse discharge in liquid at conversion into mechanical and thermal energy are given along with the review of scientific research on the application of the electrohydraulic Yutkin effect.

Keywords: high-voltage discharge, water disinfection, operating voltage, electrohydraulic effect.

One of the industrial methods of converting electrical energy into mechanical energy is the highly efficient electrohydraulic effect (EHE) performed without intermediate mechanical links (the Yutkin effect, the electrohydraulic Yutkin effect). He was the first to investigate the transition of electricity into mechanical energy, and also modeled electric discharge in liquid, established its regularities and called it electrohydraulic effect Lev Alexandrovich Yutkin.

A great contribution to the development of physics and technology of electric discharges with liquid and solid electrodes was made by specialists of various scientific schools of Russia (Akyshev Yu. S., Abdullin I. Sh., Barinov Yu. A., Belkin P. N., Gilmutdinov A. Kh., Duradzhi V. N., Kashapov N. F., Lazarenko B. R., Lebedev Yu. A., Maksimov A. I., Rybkin V. V., Slovetsky D. I., Son Ye. Ye., Tazmeyev Kh. K., Titov V. A., Shkolnik S. A., Andre P., Bruggeman P., Faure G., Jedlovsky I., Kaplan V., Krchma F., Kushner M., Leis S., Lefort A., Machala Z., Norberg S., Pongrak B., Wacher D. et al.)

The essence of this method lies in the fact that when a specially formed pulsed electrical (spark, brush and other forms) discharge is carried out inside the volume of liquid located in an open or closed vessel, a very high hydraulic pressure is created around the area, its formation, capable of performing useful mechanical work and accompanied by a series of physical and chemical phenomena.

Hydraulic impulses resulting from a discharge in liquid consist of two shocks: the main shock is hydraulic ;the second is cavitation [1]. The author L. I. Goltsova defined the directions of using EGE for the benefit of man, more than 200 methods and devices were developed, more than 150 copyright certificates for inventions were obtained in the field of application of the electrohydraulic effect in various fields of technology and economy: processing in the field of metal (stamping, expansion, cutting, cleaning); regardless of hardness crushing of rocks; obtaining various colloids; vibration technology; mining industry (drilling of wells, blasting of monoliths, laying of pits, day drifts, mines, geo- and hydro-locators; seismic exploration; in pillar-free mining); medicine (extracorporeal grinding

of stones in the kidneys, urine and gallbladder of a person); agriculture: of soil trace elements into soluble ones available for plant nutrition; cleaning, disinfection and disposal of animal waste using EHE; peat enrichment and peat fertiliser cellulose production; enrichment of animal fodder.

In fact, the nature of the electrohydraulic effect is an electrical explosion capable of deforming various materials.

In this field, which is currently one of the most dynamically developing in science, a number of studies have been done by Akishev Yu. S., Abdullin I. Sh., Barinov Y. A., Andre P., Bruggemann P., Faure G., etc., and others.

The scientific bases of electric discharge by solid electrodes are detailed in the well-known works by Yu. P. Raiser, M. N. Schneider, N. A. Yatsenko. HF electrodeless discharge is considered thoroughly in the well-known works by Dresvin S. V., Frolov V. Ya., Lelevkin V. M.

The electrohydraulic effect is used in various branches of industry and agriculture: cleaning of metal casting moulds, cleaning of power boiler pipelines, treatment of heating radiators, soil cultivation and water disinfection. The existing technical means for wastewater disinfection are expensive, heavy and unsuitable to be transported. The currently used facilities have capacitors with an operating voltage of 10-50 kilovolts, designed for voltages not exceeding 100 kilovolts, with a capacitance of 0.25 microfarads. According to the research carried out, it is possible to disinfect water with a voltage of 10 kilovolts. To do this, it is necessary to develop a laboratory electrohydraulic unit. The materials, equipment and devices to be applied are the following: power supply; transformer; capacitor; formation of inter-discharge distance; working part; shunt resistance.

The principle of the electrohydraulic effect, which is a result of the electrohydraulic shocks between the high-voltage electrodes placed in the liquid, is taken as a basis for the design and manufacture of the unit.

A block diagram of the laboratory installation is drawn up (Fig. 1

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Figure 1 - A schematic diagram of the electrohydroimpulse unit.

1 - control panel, 2 - generator, 3 - capacitor, 4 - discharge interval, 5 - protection unit, 6 - working environment.

In order to introduce the method of water disinfection at voltage not exceeding 10 kV, an experimental sample of a laboratory water disinfection unit with technical innovations in mobility and space efficiency was created [2]. It was determined that the unit consists of the power supply unit FA-5-1/300W, the high-voltage step-up transformer TDKS32-04, the capacitor K75-29A (16 kV, 1 μ F) and the molded holes for metal balls with the diameter of 18 mm and a plastic housing made of ABS material, the shunt resistance is 1 kOhm.

The scientific and practical significance of the results of the conducted research consists in the following: the assembly of the technical device or unit for water disinfection allows to carry out experimental laboratory studies of the electrohydraulic effect at voltage of not more than 10 kilovolts.

The results of direct current electric discharges with solid electrodes in liquid and experimental studies on parameters such as U , p , i , vc , lc , dc , d , electrolyte

composition and concentration are presented. The obtained experimental data were analysed and summarised [3].

Using the pulse capacitor, much more energy can be obtained, and highly efficient operations can be carried out. Formula to determine energy

However, high-frequency discharges produced by electrodes in liquid, the effect of DC electric discharges on low-pressure liquid by solid electrodes and other problems are still insufficiently studied.

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